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Article

Edge Computing Resource Allocation for Dynamic Networks: The DRUID-NET Vision and Perspective

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Abstract: The potential offered by the abundance of sensors, actuators and communications in the IoT era is hindered by the limited computational capacity of local nodes. Several key challenges should be addressed to optimally and jointly exploit the network, computing, and storage resources, guaranteeing at the same time feasibility for time-critical and mission-critical tasks. We propose the DRUID-NET framework to take upon these challenges by dynamically distributing resources when the demand is rapidly varying. It includes analytic dynamical modelling of the resources, offered workload, and networking environment, incorporating phenomena typically met in wireless communications and mobile edge computing, together with new estimators of time-varying profiles. Building on this framework, we aim to develop novel resource allocation mechanisms that explicitly include service differentiation and context-awareness, being able of guaranteeing well-defined Quality of Service (QoS) metrics. DRUID-NET goes beyond the state of the art in the design of control algorithms by incorporating resource allocation mechanisms to the decision strategy itself. To achieve these breakthroughs, we combine tools from Automata and Graph theory, Machine Learning, Modern Control Theory and Network Theory. DRUID-NET constitutes the first truly holistic, multidisciplinary approach that extends recent, albeit fragmented results from all aforementioned fields, thus bridging the gap between efforts of different communities.

Keywords: Edge Computing; Internet of Things; Mobile Robots; Resource Allocation; Control co-design

1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) consists of low-cost efficient sensors, actuators, and computing units and provides great benefits to people to synthesize a system of interrelated computing, sensing, and communication devices, that facilitates and improves everyday life, in cities and industry. IoT is foreseen to reach 500 billion devices that are connected to the Internet by 2030 [1], while the global mobile traffic is expected to increase sevenfold by 2021 [2]. Though significant improvements have been obtained in terms of hardware advances and processing capabilities at the device level, still in most cases, IoT devices (e.g. smart devices, sensors, actuators, mobile agents) cannot meet, and more importantly cannot guarantee the required high performance and/or fulfilment of time constraints, for time-critical and mission-critical IoT-enabled applications. Thus, offloading computation and energy intensive tasks to powerful computing infrastructure for further processing becomes of vital importance.

31 The success of the computation offloading, and consequently the performance of IoT-enabled
32 applications, depends on many contextual parameters, e.g the user's mobility, various wireless
33 parameters and the resource availability of the computing resources in the data center. Most of
34 the modern IoT-enabled applications rely on continuously moving people or mobile agents. Regarding
35 the latter, various types of autonomous mobile agents or unmanned vehicles are used. Typical examples
36 of these agents are the unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV), which are widely used in several human
37 activities in the context of smart city, agriculture, area surveillance, rescue missions and event coverage
38 [3]. UAVs can be used individually or in a swarm, and they are equipped with various sensors in order
39 to complete a mission or to execute their own tasks, such as trajectory planning and positioning. Their
40 limited computing resources and energy reserves do not allow local data processing. Thus, the data
41 offloading seems the only viable solution for using massively UAVs in various daily scenarios. Data
42 are transmitted through wireless links, i.e., cellular or WiFi, and the quality of the wireless connection
43 heavily depends on signal strength, interference, packet dropouts and other parameters related to the
44 wireless environment, which must be considered in the offloading decision.

45 The computation offloading aims to save time and energy at the end user's side. Cloud computing
46 seems the natural selection for offloading, as it is the prevalent service delivery model nowadays.
47 However, the high network delay for sending data over public internet counterbalances the benefits of
48 the powerful computing resources that are available at a cloud data center. Accordingly, Multi-Access
49 Edge Computing (MEC) [4] and Fog Computing [5] have arisen as promising approaches to overcome
50 this obstacle and provide the benefits of cloud computing in the proximity of the end-users. Over
51 the last few years, powerful UAVs have been considered as means to provide computing support to
52 the end-users by acting as UAV-mounted MEC servers [6]. In that respect the UAV-mounted MEC
53 servers in combination with ground MEC servers collectively create a fog computing system [7],
54 supporting end-users' applications' task offloading. Similarly, the use of clusters of UAV-mounted
55 MEC servers are suggested [8] allowing the opportunistic task offloading to the neighboring UAV
56 clusters with sufficient computing resources. In such a UAV-assisted networks, computing intensive
57 tasks are offloaded and executed in a nearby small-size edge data center, either directly connected with
58 a wireless access point, or it is embedded on the UAV itself. The key difference between cloud and edge
59 data center is that the latter has finite amount of computing resources, which requires fine-grained
60 resource management towards meeting the strict constraints of the deployed time- and mission-critical
61 applications.

62 1.1. *The DRUID-NET Perspective and Contributions*

63 This article presents the vision and perspective of the DRUID-NET (eDge computing ResoUrce
64 allocatIon for Dynamic NETworks) framework, along with a detailed description of its main concepts
65 and objectives. While considering the end-user's mobility and the parameters of the wireless
66 connection environment, the DRUID-NET framework aims at developing workload profile holistic
67 and modular dynamic performance models of IoT-enabled applications based on the appropriate
68 theoretical tools. Furthermore, the article aims to outline the control principles of novel resource
69 management systems for this kind of applications. In particular, the key research threads and topics of
70 this article are summarized as follows:

- 71 - **Workload Profile:** The IoT applications generate time-varying traffic in terms of request size and
72 number of flows. Additionally, the involved wireless communication between the mobile devices
73 and the back-end software components introduces additional uncertainties that considerably
74 affect the offloading decision and the resource scheduling at the edge computing infrastructure.
75 Contrarily to existing average traffic characteristics, building dynamic traffic profiles and
76 prediction mechanisms will enable more accurate, adaptive and successful data offloading
77 and resource allocation mechanisms.
- 78 - **Performance Modelling:** Most of the existing models for describing the performance of
79 IoT-enabled applications are empirical and usually focus on a specific performance metric, e.g.,

80 response time, throughput, energy consumption, etc. These models cannot adequately capture
81 the dynamic nature of the emerging applications, which in turn leads to either performance
82 degradation or resource over-provisioning. On the other hand, the DRUID-NET framework
83 proposes formal dynamic multi-input multi-output performance models applicable to various
84 IoT applications. This type of models enables the design of novel controllers for finer regulation
85 of Quality of Service (QoS) metrics.

- 86 - **Resource Allocation:** Usually most studies in the literature combine a static performance model
87 with solving an optimization problem. However, this approach assumes that the workload does
88 not vary significantly, which limits their validity, applicability and exploitability. In contrast
89 to these approaches, we envisage to design stabilizing controllers in order to guarantee the
90 feasibility of the resource scheduling and the performance requirements.
- 91 - **Control co-design** The DRUID-NET framework examines specifically the case where the
92 application is the controller design and its implementation for dynamic processes. In this
93 setting, the performance of the closed-loop system is considered in the overall application
94 performance. The control co-design approach aims to design feedback mechanisms achieving
95 closed-loop system properties such as reachability, stabilization and other complex specifications,
96 and simultaneously design and implement resource allocation algorithms for the dynamic
97 network.

98 The rest of the article is organized as follows. In Section 2, the current state of the art is presented.
99 Section 3 demonstrates the conceptual architecture of the DRUID-NET framework, while Section 4
100 describes three IoT-enabled use cases where the proposed solution is applicable. Finally, Section 5
101 draws the conclusions and future directives of our research.

102 2. Related Work & Motivation

103 This section provides a thorough yet comprehensive presentation of the most relative studies to the
104 DRUID-NET framework, in the recent literature. Aligned with the DRUID-NET objectives, Abdelzaher
105 et al. [9] presented five challenges on IoT applications and Edge Computing. This study focused
106 mostly on deep learning-based application modeling, optimal offloading, closed loop guarantees and
107 collaborative offloading. Towards these directions, the related work is categorized under three major
108 classes; (i) IoT workload profile, (ii) performance modelling and resource allocation and (iii) control
109 co-design.

110 2.1. IoT Workload profile

111 The estimation of the workload and communication patterns in IoT-Fog/Edge networks, has only
112 been little explored due the high heterogeneity of co-existing devices. Nevertheless, there is no doubt
113 that the proper estimation of the offered workload and communication patterns could lead to a more
114 efficient utilisation of the underlying infrastructure.

115 Authors in [10] considered a two-tier network architecture consisting of shallow and deep
116 cloudlets, and explored the benefits of hierarchical capacity provisioning based on queuing analysis.
117 Although shown to be efficient in very specific cases, this approach cannot be generalized in
118 principle. Osmotic Computing [11] relied on the deployment of lightweight microservices on
119 resource-constrained IoT platforms at the network edge, coupled with more complex microservices
120 running on large-scale datacenters. MobiQoR [12] introduced a new metric, Quality of Results, to
121 validate the quality of edge resource deployment. Nevertheless, none of these approaches attempted to
122 estimate the IoT workload, which in turn could significantly enhance the corresponding deployments.
123 Authors in [13] and subsequently in [14] analysed the resource allocation of a three-layer infrastructure
124 (IoT, Edge, Cloud) under dynamic network conditions. However, they took into consideration the
125 dynamic opt-in and out of IoT devices into the network, while ignoring their instantaneous workload
126 generation. To the best of our knowledge, the only attempts to estimate workload are referring to the
127 cloud utilization [15,16], and as such they did not capture the locality of the heterogeneous IoT traffics.

128 A promising approach to derive workload profile is to use machine learning techniques. Applying
129 deep or machine learning techniques for IoT applications is not new [17], but most of the time they are
130 centralized and do not need any adaptation to fit specific IoT devices limitations. In DRUID-NET, we
131 will rely on existing estimation methods, such as [18], to estimate the workload of hardware constrained
132 devices. In existing works the focus is placed on one specific resource each time (e.g. energy, memory,
133 computing, etc) [19]. The DRUID-NET framework aims at extending them to multiple resources, while
134 combining these approaches with predictive methods, which have only been slightly explored for
135 IoT due to resource limitations. So far, methods such as ARIMA [20], deadreckoning [21], Kalman
136 filters [22], Thompson sampling [23] or Bayesian approaches [24] have mainly been investigated for
137 navigation and position prediction [20], data reduction [24], link prediction [25] or medium occupation
138 [23]. Our aim is to provide a unique distributed and adaptive multi-resource estimation and prediction
139 suitable for IoT devices. The DRUID-NET goal is to derive some communication patterns, clearly
140 defined in time and size, towards assessing the need in edge resources in time and space. This
141 edge-resource sizing combined with performance modeling, controlled mobility of edge-resource and
142 resource allocation, will enable the adaptive deployment of sufficient resources, on demand and in an
143 efficient manner.

144 2.2. Performance modeling and resource allocation in Cloud and Edge Computing

145 Resource allocation has become one of the most important open research problems in Cloud and
146 Edge computing and IoT. In cloud computing environment, the computing resources are assumed
147 to be infinite, thus, static or empirical models combined with coarse resource scheduling techniques
148 have been shown sufficient to provide high performance through over-provisioning. However,
149 these approaches are neither optimal nor able to provide QoS guarantees. Regarding application's
150 performance modeling, the empirical or fixed models considered already known request sizes and
151 execution times, which are not only hardware-specific, but generally very difficult to be precisely
152 computed. Furthermore, many studies relied on queuing models [26], e.g. G/G/1 or G/G/n, which
153 are reliable only for steady state. It is obvious that this kind of modelling cannot capture transient
154 phenomena due to dynamic workload demand. With this capacity, System Theory [27] can provide
155 dynamic modeling methodologies, appropriate for Cloud/IoT-based applications. The interesting
156 reader may refer to survey [28] for an extended analysis of control theoretic approaches on performance
157 modeling and cloud elasticity. Close to DRUID-NET concepts, Dechouniotis et al. [29] proposed Linear
158 Parameter Varying (LPV) modelling of cloud applications combined with set-theoretic controllers to
159 guarantee feasible solution of the elasticity in cloud data centers, while Leontiou et al. [30] derived
160 fuzzy Takagi-Sugeno models and designed robust controllers to address simultaneously the problems
161 of vertical and horizontal scaling, and load balancing with stability guarantee.

162 Contrarily to cloud computing, the resources of edge computing are rather limited, thus, static
163 allocation techniques cannot achieve optimal resource utilization. Furthermore, modern time- and
164 mission-critical IoT-enabled applications [31,32] have strict performance requirements that only
165 dynamic modeling and intelligent allocation algorithms can guarantee. Similarly to cloud, in the edge
166 computing context, most of relative studies proposed static models alongside with the optimization
167 of a single performance criterion, e.g. energy consumption or response time. Towards this direction,
168 Sonmez et al. [33] proposed a two-stage fuzzy mechanism for offloading requests to edge and
169 cloud infrastructure. The set of fuzzy rules are empirically decided and the VM (Virtual Machine)
170 utilization modeling is threshold-based, which is applicable only for specific types of IoT applications.
171 Queec [34] formulates the problem of scheduling multi-user tasks to multiple edge nodes as an
172 optimization problem which minimizes the overall offloading latency of all tasks. Jalali et al. [35]
173 analysed fixed flow-based and time-based energy consumption models and they presented a detailed
174 comparison on energy consumption between cloud and edge computing systems under various
175 network settings. Lyu et al. [36] presented a collaborative Cloud-MEC-IoT architecture and proposed
176 a request modelling scheme and an admission control framework to address the scalability problem of

177 these platforms. Although the authors considered heterogeneous edge resources, the computation
178 model was not dynamic. The authors of [37] addressed both the problems of network selection and
179 service placement for MEC infrastructure. Towards the reduction of the complexity of the general
180 problem, they decomposed it into a series of sub-problems and solved them in an iterative fashion.
181 However, the proposed performance model focused only on network related parameters ignoring the
182 processing time of the application.

183 In the 5G era, Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) and Software Defined Networks (SDN)
184 play key role for the realization of many type of verticals, which are comprised by several IoT
185 applications. In this context, virtualized and isolated Service Chains (SCs) comprised of a series of
186 Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) implemented as VMs need to be deployed in the available MEC
187 infrastructure to offer networking services to the IoT traffic. Normally, the objective of this kind of
188 resource allocation mechanism aims to minimize the overall deployment cost (e.g. the computational
189 and communication resources that a SC needs in order to be provisioned) [38]. Another common
190 approach is to minimize the overall delay, since several IoT applications are characterized as mission
191 critical and delay sensitive. Thus, a valid approach is to utilize the MEC resources that are closer to the
192 IoT devices [39]. An alternative approach to minimize the delay is to create resource clusters inside the
193 MEC infrastructure, where the various requested SCs can be deployed [40]. Minimizing the number
194 of clusters and appropriately positioning the VNFs can lead to a reduction of the communication
195 delay. Efforts have also been dedicated to optimize the energy consumption. The authors of [41]
196 modelled the energy dissipation of the resources in the IoT and MEC infrastructures and constructed a
197 Linear Programming algorithm to carefully select the resources to place the SCs. Another objective
198 focuses on the optimal allocation and scheduling of the available edge resources. This objective can
199 be translated into either: a) minimizing the overall resource usage, to enable multiple heterogeneous
200 SCs, servicing heterogeneous IoT applications, to co-exist in the MEC layer [42], or b) minimizing
201 the resource idleness of the infrastructure [43]. Load balancing can also be applied by minimizing
202 the maximum link utilization and reducing the bandwidth consumption [44]. This can be achieved
203 by adopting appropriate queuing and QoS modeling during the optimization problem to minimize
204 the resource utilization [45]. Even though all the above solutions target valid and open challenges
205 of resource allocation in the IoT/MEC, they only propose static approaches failing to provide a
206 holistic mechanism that takes into consideration a multi-objective and dynamic solution. Following
207 the performance modeling and control design principles of [9,46], DRUID-NET aspires to provide
208 multi-variable dynamic models and design modern control methodologies that ensure the desired
209 user's performance requirements and optimize the utilization objectives of the infrastructure provider
210 simultaneously.

211 *2.3. Control-theoretic resource allocation and control co-design*

212 In control theory, the effect of a shared, imperfect communication network between the controller
213 and the sensor/actuator network has been studied extensively for almost three decades, generating the
214 separate branch of Networked Control Systems (NCS), [47,48]. NCS suffer from many non-idealities.
215 For instance, networked induced delays or, even worse, packet dropouts occur, as the information
216 from the sensor to the controller or from the controller to actuator(s) can be lost in a time interval.
217 Moreover, due to the limited energy available at decentralized nodes, bandwidth can be low, so that the
218 effect of quantization in the communication channels may not be neglected. Also, switching or hybrid
219 phenomena may occur due to the asynchrony between disconnected agents, or due to event-triggered
220 strategies. Finally, the computational problem, to be performed at the nodes, may be part of a global
221 optimization problem, which is split into decentralized subtasks.

222 Several methods have addressed these non-idealities separately. Time delays, for instance, have
223 been tackled utilizing perturbation theory, Lyapunov stability theory and hybrid systems analysis,
224 but also probabilistic methods involving Markov chains and stochastic automata [49]. Quantization
225 problems have led to a rich literature, where the controllability of a plant subject to quantized control

226 is ruled by the so-called *entropy* of the system [50]. From the hybrid control point of view, researchers
227 from real time computing have dealt with the schedulability problem of distributed control settings,
228 leading to the design of several protocols for a stable closed-loop behaviour, [51–53]. Decentralised
229 computation/optimization has been another major topic of research in Systems and Control [54]. Here,
230 though the state of the art is rich, the interaction of this constraint with others is not well understood
231 and studied. Let us note however that the consensus problem has been deeply studied, in many
232 settings, e.g. quantized communications [55].

233 Additionally to the stochastic results [56], recent theoretical work on the controllability and
234 observability properties of the NCS [57] has shown that a more refined modelling of the communication
235 network allows the proper definition and verification of such properties, thus adding new tools to
236 the NCS community. Furthermore, proof-of-concept work has shown that under a new modeling
237 framework for hybrid systems and specifically constrained switching systems [58], the control
238 performance can be directly associated with the network quality [59].

239 Rather than designing the control and communication protocol in two steps, co-design methods
240 aim to synthesize simultaneously controllers and the communication patterns (sampling, delays,
241 scheduling protocols). Applied only to networked control systems with constrained communication
242 resources so far, co-design methods have been extensively studied the last decade [60–63]. Perhaps the
243 most relevant breakthrough in this area is the emergence of event-triggered and self-triggered control
244 mechanisms, that allow asynchronous sampling, thus reducing the network traffic, while at the same
245 time behaving sub-optimally [64–66].

246 Nevertheless, there is limited work on the co-design of controllers taking into account
247 simultaneously more than one phenomena (schedulability, network utilization, edge resource
248 utilization, energy consumption etc.) caused by the distribution of computing and communication
249 resources. It is anticipated that the research developments in the next decades, will allow to encapsulate,
250 compare, and subsequently alter the impact of the several non-idealities, and this in turn will have a
251 significant impact on future control applications, where resources must be used parsimoniously, in
252 balance with the constraints and the overall considered objective. This will require and motivate new
253 paradigms in Systems and Controls, where multi-objective optimization, model-free (data-driven)
254 approaches, approximate optimality (however with firm safety guarantees), reconfigurability, and
255 resilience take a central place.

256 3. DRUID-NET Conceptual Architecture

257 Figure 1 illustrates a high-level overview of the overall DRUID-NET framework. The architecture
258 follows the NFV/SDN paradigm and separates the flow of information into control and data planes.
259 At the lowest layer, the IoT applications are deployed, and the generated workload (data flow) can be
260 offloaded for further processing at the upper level of Edge Computing. In this layer, any component of
261 the application is provided as a virtualized service. As it is shown in the figure, a virtualized service
262 corresponds either to IoT specific functionalities, e.g. path planning and image recognition, or control
263 components such as learning algorithms or optimization solvers. The modelling and control framework
264 collects information (control flow) about the status of the computing and network infrastructure at the
265 edge computing level in order to create workload-resource profiles, update the performance model
266 for every application, and realize the feedback control mechanism for the resource allocation, while
267 simultaneously implementing a resource-aware control strategy for the cyber-physical system to be
268 controlled (control flow). This holistic approach allows the application's dynamical modelling taking
269 various contextual information into account. Furthermore, the controller co-design treats the resource
270 allocation algorithms as application components in the virtualized services. Each major component of
271 the modelling and control framework is described in more detail in the following subsections.

Figure 1. Conceptual Architecture

272 3.1. IoT Workload Profiling

273 As mentioned before, a major challenge for solving the resource allocation problem in edge
 274 computing settings is to predict the time-varying characteristics of the workload/traffic, as different
 275 traffic flows and volatile conditions can influence significantly the resource allocation mechanism.
 276 Aspects such as the load generated from an IoT device, latency specifications, the transmitting data
 277 frequency, the wireless protocol, the mobility of the devices, and the number of devices associated
 278 with the IoT gateway, change the amount of resources requested from the edge, while also influencing
 279 the scheduling process. Till now, only generic traffic models have been proposed to estimate the traffic
 280 aggregated at the edge layer, while stationary IoT devices are assumed, leading to a static rate model,
 281 which however limits its effectiveness and applicability in real scenarios.

282 Going a step beyond from the pertinent literature, which only considers average and general
 283 traffic characteristics of the IoT applications (e.g. Brownian motion as one-fits-all model), DRUID-NET
 284 framework aims to differentiate and categorize the requirements of different IoT applications using
 285 appropriate data analytic and mathematical models. In particular, we classify and categorize the IoT
 286 applications by leveraging the transmission patterns, the spatial and temporal correlation of the traffic,
 287 as well as other traffic related characteristics such as the frame size distribution, and the burstiness of
 288 the traffic of the IoT applications. The novelty of this approach is that we create prediction mechanisms
 289 to treat the dynamics and uncertainty in the corresponding traffic profiles. Each predictive mechanism
 290 targets specific categories of IoT applications with similar requirements and characteristics to define
 291 the type, the size, as well as the time and the location of the requested resources. Furthermore, with this
 292 approach we can dispose the erroneous assumption that specific tasks are associated with static and
 293 pre-specified resource footprints. In contrast, we replace this analogy with an opportunistic association

294 between the requested resources and the IoT traffic dynamicity, thus introducing a holistic mechanism
295 inspired by data analytics, and traffic analysis methods.

296 3.1.1. IoT applications classification

297 A first classification of the IoT applications can be produced by simply answering yes or no, to
298 questions regarding the involved "things"/devices. Indicative such questions can be identified as
299 follows: i) Are the devices heterogeneous? ii) Are they battery-powered? iii) Are they sending data
300 with high or low frequency? iv) Are they data rich (e.g. multiple number of sensor measurements)? v)
301 Are the devices mobile?

302 The answer to such questions will help us to create a first clustering of the IoT applications. These
303 clusters will contain IoT applications with similar device characteristics and behavior. Nonetheless,
304 this first-phase categorization does not necessarily mean that the IoT applications belonging in the
305 same cluster will present the same exactly resource requirements at the Edge. The reason is that
306 different network access technologies can significantly affect the network requirements of the IoT
307 applications. For example, different access technologies (e.g. LoRaWAN, Wi-Fi, IEEE 802.15.4, cellular,
308 etc.) have different characteristics in terms of packet length, transmission range supported, MAC
309 mechanisms, topological characteristics of the associated IoT devices (e.g. star, mesh, peer-to-peer),
310 number of device connections supported, etc.

311 Thus, DRUID-NET takes into consideration both the functional and network requirements of the
312 IoT applications in order to provide a complete and realistic IoT application classification.

313 3.1.2. IoT applications workload prediction

314 The above categorization will help us to extract the workload generated from each cluster of
315 applications in terms of bandwidth, latency and other important Key performance Indicators (KPIs)
316 during the offloading of IoT tasks to the Edge. Specifically, through this approach we can propose
317 appropriate mathematical models to simulate the traffic behavior of the various IoT applications.
318 Nonetheless, even with this modeling a lot of ambiguity will exist. The reason is that IoT access
319 networks include several uncertainties, usually being wireless, lossy, and unreliable. Hence, the goal
320 of DRUID-NET is not only to categorise and classify IoT applications based on their traffic profiling,
321 but to also apply network analytics to make the communication as deterministic as possible.

322 Our goal is to replace the so far average estimates of the IoT applications with instantaneous and
323 accurate transmission metrics. To this end, appropriate machine learning algorithms (i.e. Thompson,
324 ARMA, Bayesian) need to be integrated in the traffic profiling in order to learn and predict the
325 network conditions between the IoT and the Edge. This can be decisive in the performance of the
326 subsequent resource allocation at the Edge. The Edge controller will be able to adapt to and predict
327 the changing workload arriving at the Edge infrastructure, creating a holistic and realistic resource
328 allocation approach.

329 3.2. Performance Modelling

330 The available resource models are usually single-input single-output. Energy or response time
331 are typically the model's outputs, while computing resources (e.g. CPU, memory), incoming requests,
332 and network bandwidth are the control variables. In most of the current studies, the relation between
333 input and output is fixed and empirically derived. For example, the processing time of a request is
334 proportional to its file size and inversely proportional of the service rate measured in CPU cycles or
335 millions of instructions per second. Although this assumption is reasonable, the actual processing
336 time depends on several time-varying parameters, which are not easily measured. Furthermore, in
337 combination with static resource allocation mechanisms, the offloading decision performs adequately
338 only for specific operating conditions, being unable to guarantee stability under fluctuating workload
339 and heterogeneous IoT communication infrastructure.

340 Contrary to current approaches that provide empirical static models, we aim to develop formal,
341 realistic and dynamic traffic and resource models applicable to emulate the generated traffic from
342 various IoT applications. For this purpose, DRUID-NET adopts hybrid dynamical models [67] that
343 have the capacity to include several performance metrics (i.e. state variables) and resources as control
344 parameters (input variables). This type of modelling takes into account in a single formulation
345 the various contributions of the diverse objectives and constraints to the performance/cost. This
346 framework moreover allows to discover the tradeoffs between accuracy, complexity of representation
347 and real-time feasibility of the resource allocation strategy. Furthermore, the chosen framework
348 will be capable of capturing structural changes interpreted as discrete jumps in the dynamics, e.g.,
349 user mobility, change in wireless protocols and topology, addition/removal of edge servers. Finally,
350 alongside with the dynamic models, the DRUID-NET framework aims to identify the uncertainties of
351 these models and quantify their boundaries in order to facilitate the design of the respective control
352 laws.

353 3.3. Resource Allocation

354 The workload profile estimator and the dynamic model of the resources and overall status of
355 the network/servers, provides the foundation upon which the resource allocation algorithm will be
356 developed. Specifically, the objective is to develop a joint communication, computing and storing
357 virtualization paradigm that is updated and adapted dynamically. For this purpose, we consider
358 the problem of simultaneously (i) allocating storage, computing and communication resources, (ii)
359 modifying network topology/ protocol, and (iii) structuring the edge computing data centres (such
360 as VMs distribution). Two distinct approaches relating to static and dynamic resource allocation, are
361 considered.

362 3.3.1. Static resource allocation

363 In this approach we do not take into account the dynamic nature of the processes under study,
364 however, we consider the full resource allocation problem. The method is oriented towards solving
365 multi-objective optimization problems fast, that will in turn provide the optimal operating point for
366 the communication network, and the computing and storage allocation in the edge/cloud servers.
367 Our goal is to describe the complex interrelations between the aforementioned resources in an analytic
368 manner, merging available models, e.g., from queuing theory and Markov models. Next, we plan to
369 solve the optimization problems using mixed-integer, linear, and nonlinear programming. Since the
370 complexity of these problems does not allow often exact real-time solutions, our intention is to propose
371 approximate solution algorithms that provide guarantees of the level of suboptimality of the identified
372 solution. Additionally, we will employ machine learning algorithms to relax the complexity of these
373 highly nonlinear/nonconvex problems so they can be solved in real-time, thus respecting hard time
374 constraints. This approach will focus on problems involving complex specifications and mostly static
375 models, aiming to maximize the QoS delivered.

376 3.3.2. Dynamic resource allocation

377 In this approach, the DRUID-NET framework proposes dynamic control-theoretic resource
378 allocation mechanisms. Utilising the models established by capturing the performance metrics
379 dynamics in a hybrid dynamical system, our goal is to follow control-theoretic approaches that
380 provide formal guarantees on important properties describing the resource allocation problem. For
381 example, a main objective is to provide guarantees of the speed of convergence of the performance
382 metrics to a pre-determined range, defined by translating the QoS requirements to mathematical
383 statements. Moreover, our goal is to provide decision mechanisms that allow structural changes in
384 some cases (for example turning on and off edge servers in a cluster, changing the topology in a
385 communication network), together with continuous strategies (such as CPU and memory utilisation in
386 a server). The natural, main challenge in this approach is the scalability of the decision algorithm, which

387 will be tackled by proposing smart allocation strategies that allow tradeoffs between performance and
388 real-time implementation. Another challenge is to establish resource allocation mechanisms using only
389 partial information, which is the most realistic scenario. This issue will be addressed by proposing
390 distributed control mechanisms that take continuously into account local information and receive only
391 intermittently information about the states of the whole system.

392 *3.4. Co-design of controllers*

393 As we have mentioned before, in the broad field of Systems and Control, several different
394 paradigms have emerged in the last decades, to deal with the control of IoT-enabled cyber-physical
395 systems. Indicative examples include hybrid behaviour, quantized control, varying delays,
396 safety-criticality, nonlinear control, etc. Although these challenges are typically met together in
397 IoT environments, the research activities have led to disconnected communities, and likewise very
398 specific and custom control techniques, that limit their implementability in a holistic framework.
399 In a real-life IoT control application, these non-idealities take place all together. We argue that the
400 different paradigms separately introduced for each of these non-idealities are hard to reconcile, thus
401 the DRUID-NET framework is devoted to deploying the theoretical results in actual applications.

402 Modern IoT applications need controllers that address a mixture of these undesired phenomena.
403 Our goal is to establish a formal decision mechanism that will be able to change the provisioning
404 of the resources in real time, adapt its control objective to the available bandwidth, weigh the cost
405 of communication with respect to the advantage of involving decentralized agents and eventually
406 address a multitude of practical challenges appearing in networked, resource-constrained control
407 applications. Such a new generation of controllers will be made possible by the merging of two sets of
408 hybrid models, namely a) the performance model having as internal variables performance metrics of
409 the infrastructure and as inputs the resource distribution and utilization, and b) the process model
410 (having, for example, variables related to position, orientation, velocity and acceleration of mobile
411 agents, lighting conditions, room temperature, mode of operation of sensors etc). To provide an
412 example of the challenges that will be met in this setting, let us raise the following question: what
413 do traditional data-rate theorems from quantized control (see, e.g. [68]) become in an environment
414 with packet losses and varying delays, and varying computational resources? Another important line
415 of research that will be necessary to follow in a time-varying resources setting is to categorize and
416 model the complexity of the control algorithms. Allowing their dynamic adjustment will eventually
417 provide the coupling between the process/application to be controlled and the control algorithm
418 resource provisioning. In turn, this will enable (i) the establishment of real-time control mechanisms
419 with formal guarantees for the closed-loop system, and (ii) the optimal utilisation of resources, either
420 in the network or the edge.

421 **4. IoT-enabled applications**

422 The proposed architecture is generic enough offering a holistic paradigm, while its estimation,
423 modeling and control methodologies are applicable in several categories of IoT applications, such
424 as the ones based on mobile agents (e.g., UAVs) or designed for crowded smart areas or emergency
425 scenarios. The following subsections demonstrate three representative use cases of the DRUID-NET
426 framework.

427 *4.1. Human-Robot Collaboration*

428 Collaborative robotics is a prerequisite for Industry 4.0, especially in the Industrial Internet of
429 Things setting. The current trend is to produce and program robots that have the capability to work
430 together, or in close proximity, to humans in a shared environment. Removing a physical (or virtual)
431 cage from the robot brings many challenges, the most critical of which is guaranteeing safety / avoiding
432 collision, without leading to an unsatisfactory performance, e.g., the robot working in a non-acceptable
433 speed. The setting can be extended to the case where there are many robotic agents and humans

Figure 2. Human-Robot Collaboration

434 sharing the factory floor, or any other indoor or outdoor environment, e.g., a logistics warehouse, an
 435 airport, swarm UAVs networks etc. In all aforementioned cases, similar challenges appear, namely: (i)
 436 intermittent and noisy measurements of the position of the agents either by static sensors or sensors
 437 mounted on the robots, (ii) faulty wireless communication networks, (iii) stringent safety specifications
 438 as humans and robots move freely in the same environment, (iv) time-critical specifications. These
 439 challenges become harder when the computing/storing/communication resources are limited, or not
 440 always available to a control application, which is the typical case. Thus far, a few approaches, aligned
 441 with the ones appearing in the cyber-physical systems control problems, take explicitly into account a
 442 part of these challenges, e.g., [69]. Controllers, which are co-designed with the resource allocation and
 443 computation offloading mechanisms, can be used for human-robot collaboration in the IoT-enabled
 444 environment or for real-time, large scale coordination of mobile robots. It should be noted that an
 445 additional control challenge in this case, additional to the presence of constraints, is the complex
 446 temporal specifications that need to be satisfied. Currently, the control objective has moved away from
 447 just ensuring stability or tracking for a prespecified set of reference trajectories, to satisfying statements,
 448 for example “robot A and B should collaborate towards a task X and eventually return to their initial
 449 positions if these positions are not occupied”, as shown in Figure 2. These control applications are often
 450 time-critical as well as safety-critical, thus, a very careful co-design procedure should be developed for
 451 the controller that leads to formal guarantees without requiring many, possibly idle, resources.

452 This scenario, enables and is enabled by, a combination of almost all components of the
 453 DRUID-NET framework, namely workload and resource estimation, and control co-design of a
 454 set of control applications in a platform where resources are shared and their availability is volatile.

4.2. Rapid Resource Deployment for Physical Disaster Scenarios

In the case of a physical disaster, the fixed communication infrastructure could be destroyed or unavailable due to high workload demand. Furthermore, for rescue operations it could be critical to deploy additional on-demand computing and network resources at the proper place and time, in order to alleviate any remaining network infrastructure and collect data from remaining communicating devices such as mobile phones or sensors, towards helping to locate and rescue survivors. Mobile agents, especially UAVs, are suitable for this kind of missions and can provide additional edge resources capable of processing the data at low latency and organizing the rescue operation. In order to serve the survivors devices as much as possible, there is a need to predict the kind and amount of resources these devices will request and the location of these resources. Some UAV-mounted edge resources may need to be deployed sporadically and temporarily at different locations based on IoT devices needs and mobility. Thus, there is a need to anticipate the deployment of edge services and to estimate the time they will be required at a given place to decide whether it is worth deploying durable edge resources, or instead mobile temporary resources could suffice. In this latter case, the estimation of the location and quantity of required resources should be anticipated to allow their timely deployment. The deployment of edge resources will be such that a maximum of IoT devices can be served within the required latency, either directly or through multi-hop communications. Direct communications will be favored for devices with very-low latency requirements, while multi-hop communications could be used for weaker latency requirements non-necessary communications. The trajectory of distributed UAV should be consciously planned accordingly, taking in consideration the time restrictions (robots should be deployed at the proper place before we need them).

Figure 3 illustrates the operation of the proposed framework under a physical disaster scenario, such as for example the occurrence of a gas leakage in a large factory. In this case, swarms of mobile robots will be deployed in order to find victims or survivors that require immediate medical assistance. Two types of mobile robots can be deployed, namely, i) Unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) and ii) UAVs. UGVs will cover the ground area (x,y dimensions), while UaVs can provide a certain altitude coverage (z dimension) or coverage in non accessible areas by the UGVs (e.g. upper floors, atriums, etc.). Normally, we expect to find more obstacles in the ground area (e.g. offices, machines, shelves), which can be translated in a higher number of UGVs in comparison with the UAVs (a ratio of 2:1), as shown in Figure 3. The goal of the interconnected UAVs is to locate living or dead persons, while at the same time send footage of the interior of the factory in order to create a 3D visualization of the area. In this manner, the users of the application (e.g. fire brigade) can immediately detect persons in need and send help to the corresponding location, eliminating the risk of long exposure to harmful gas for the rescuers. For the path planning of the mobile agents, the robots will be capable of detecting the Wi-Fi or LTE preamble and accordingly plan the route towards the source of the signal. The notion behind this behavior is that normally people have in close vicinity their mobile phones or other wireless devices (e.g. smart watches). This will facilitate the path planning and the pointless roaming of the UAVs in space. In order to prioritize the traffic and eliminate the impact of poor wireless communication, the swarm of robots can intensify the load of images/video and increase their quality only in areas with high probability of detecting a person, and send this traffic at the Edge for further processing. UGVs can approach the victims and sense if they are living or unconscious (e.g. detect eye movement, detect sound, etc.). When a UGV finds a survivor it can communicate with the UAV of the swarm near by, which in turn can lower its altitude close to the position of the person in need and drop an oxygen mask, until help arrives.

In this case, using swarms of mobile robots will assist in eliminating the non-essential communications. Combining service differentiation and smart data offloading to UAVs, there will be reduction of any unnecessary communication between users and overhead due to extensive signaling. Since the number of available robots may still be inadequate to serve all ground services, the prioritization of the applications, flows and devices is of paramount importance for the success of critical missions. Under these circumstances, the priority will be given to the areas with many

Figure 3. Rapid Resource Development for Physical Disasters

505 victims or of major importance for the completion of the mission, thus, the available swarms of mobile
 506 robots should be distributed accordingly. Even in the case of homogeneous UGVs and UAVs with
 507 identical computing and networking capabilities, the optimal allocation of UAVs or UGVs formulates
 508 a dynamic optimisation problem, which depends on the size of the damaged area, the communication
 509 ranges of both UGVs and UAVs, the flying altitude of UAVs, the propagation conditions, the data
 510 communication requirements (amount of data, frequency of collection, etc) and the number and type of
 511 devices to serve. For example, if the victims are equally spread in different locations, the robot swarms
 512 would be equally scattered to deploy their resources in these areas so that the maximum number of
 513 devices would be served directly. On the other hand, the mobile robots will be driven to the most
 514 damaged area in order to serve the required network traffic.

515 This scenario illustrates the use and combination of the different control components of the
 516 DRUID-NET framework, and in particular: 1) workload estimation in quantity, time and space, 2)
 517 resource allocation (tasks assignments to UAV and/or robots) and 3) path trajectory.

518 4.3. Mobility-aware Edge Computing

519 Most of the modern smart city applications rely on mobile end-devices of continuously moving
 520 humans. Thus, the user's mobility is a dominant parameter of IoT systems. As shown in Figure 4, in the
 521 case of an urban touristic areas, e.g., museums and squares, the visitors collect information about Points
 522 of Interests (PoIs) (i.e., exhibits or social events) using their mobile devices. For example, leveraging
 523 the augmented or virtual reality technologies, they can retrieve media-enriched information about
 524 the surrounding PoIs. However, it is prohibited for the mobile end-devices with limited resources to
 525 run this type of applications locally. Thus, the edge computing infrastructure is essential to host the
 526 smart applications and meet the user's QoS requirements. Additionally, in crowded touristic areas, the

Figure 4. Mobility-Aware Edge Computing

527 number of visitors varies significantly during short-term (i.e. a day) or long-term periods (summer or
 528 winter), therefore, an accurate prediction methodology is important for optimal resource scheduling.
 529 Moreover, the offloading decision should be based on both the user's transmission capability and
 530 the availability of edge resources. With this capacity, in order to maximize the admittance of users,
 531 the main features of the overall generated traffic should be extracted alongside with patterns of the
 532 user's mobility. Then, utilizing the dynamic models, effective controllers can be designed towards the
 533 horizontal and vertical scaling of resources and the simultaneous guarantee of any QoS and Quality of
 534 Experiment (QoE) requirements.

535 This use case illustrates the necessity and the collaboration of the involved components of the
 536 DRUID-NET framework. Particularly, workload estimation, dynamic performance modeling and
 537 resource allocation components interact to meet the respective requirements and optimize the resource
 538 utilization under varying workload conditions.

539 5. Conclusions

540 This article presents the most important challenges of IoT-enabled applications, along with
 541 the perspective and the basic concepts and objectives of the novel DRUID-NET framework. The
 542 corresponding components of the DRUID-NET framework are carefully designed to address several
 543 emerging challenges at any level of the IoT/Edge/Cloud system, stemming from mobile end-devices
 544 up to powerful cloud data servers.

545 In particular, the workload estimation aims to create a profile of IoT applications that includes
 546 features of the generated data, parameters of the wireless connection and patterns of the user's mobility.
 547 The performance modeling components identify the multi-input multi-output dynamical systems that
 548 capture the dynamic operation of the applications, and are utilized to design the resource allocation
 549 and the offloading decision strategies. The resource allocation component is in turn responsible for
 550 deciding any control action at any level of the hierarchical system. Depending on the objectives of
 551 the controller, the resource allocation can be either static or dynamic, providing guarantees on QoS

552 metrics, e.g. response time or energy consumption, and system properties, such as stability. Finally, the
 553 co-design of the controllers enables the binding between the IoT application and the resource control
 554 algorithm in order to provide guarantees for the closed-loop system.

555 The DRUID-NET framework aspires to verify its modular architecture and components through
 556 different IoT scenarios. These use cases are carefully selected in order to cover all main challenging
 557 and emerging aspects of the IoT applications and Edge computing paradigm.

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563 Abbreviations

564 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

565 MDPI & Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute
 DOAJ & Directory of open access journals
 IoT & Internet of Things
 UAV & Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
 UGV & Unmanned Ground Vehicles
 MEC & Multi-access Edge Computing
 DRUID-NET & eDge computing ResoUrce allocatIon for Dynamic NETworks
 566 QoS & Quality of Service
 QoE & Quality of Experience
 NFV & Network Functions Virtualization
 SDN & Software Defined Networks
 5G & Fifth Generation
 SC & Service Chain
 VNF & Virtualized Network Function
 VM & Virtual Machine
 NCS & Networked Control Systems

567 References

- 568 1. Cisco. Cisco White Paper. Internet of things at a glance., 2017.
- 569 2. Ericsson. Ericsson mobility report - q4, 2018.
- 570 3. Hayat, S.; Yanmaz, E.; Muzaffar, R. Survey on unmanned aerial vehicle networks for civil applications: A
 571 communications viewpoint. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* **2016**, *18*, 2624–2661.
- 572 4. ETSI. ETSI Multi-access Edge Computing., 2019.
- 573 5. Yousefpour, A.; Fung, C.; Nguyen, T.; Kadiyala, K.; Jalali, F.; Niakanlahiji, A.; Kong, J.; Jue, J. All one needs
 574 to know about fog computing and related edge computing paradigms: A complete survey. *Elsevier Journal
 575 of Systems Architecture* **2019**, *98*, 289 – 330. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sysarc.2019.02.009>.
- 576 6. Jeong, S.; Simeone, O.; Kang, J. Mobile edge computing via a UAV-mounted cloudlet: Optimization of bit
 577 allocation and path planning. *IEEE Transaction on Vehicular Technology* **2017**, *67*, 2049–2063.
- 578 7. He, D.; Qiao, Y.; Chan, S.; Guizani, N. Flight security and safety of drones in airborne fog computing
 579 systems. *IEEE Communications Magazine* **2018**, *56*, 66–71.
- 580 8. Valentino, R.; Jung, W.S.; Ko, Y.B. Opportunistic computational offloading system for clusters of drones.
 581 20th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology. IEEE, 2018, pp. 303–306.
- 582 9. Abdelzaher, T.; Hao, Y.; Jayarajah, K.; Misra, A.; Skarin, P.; Yao, S.; Weerakoon, D.; undefinedrżén, K.
 583 Five Challenges in Cloud-Enabled Intelligence and Control. *ACM Trans. Internet Technol.* **2020**, *20*.
 584 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3366021>.
- 585 10. Kiani, A.; Ansari, N.; Khreishah, A. Hierarchical Capacity Provisioning for Fog Computing. *IEEE/ACM
 586 Transactions on Networking* **2019**, *27*, 962–971. doi:10.1109/TNET.2019.2906638.

- 587 11. Villari, M.; Fazio, M.; Dustdar, S.; Rana, O.; Ranjan, R. Osmotic Computing: A New Paradigm for
588 Edge/Cloud Integration. *IEEE Cloud Computing* **2016**, *3*, 76–83. doi:10.1109/MCC.2016.124.
- 589 12. Li, Y.; Chen, Y.; Lan, T.; Venkataramani, G. MobiQoR: Pushing the Envelope of Mobile Edge Computing
590 Via Quality-of-Result Optimization. 2017 IEEE 37th International Conference on Distributed Computing
591 Systems (ICDCS), 2017, pp. 1261–1270. doi:10.1109/ICDCS.2017.54.
- 592 13. Leivadeas, A.; Falkner, M.; Lambadaris, I.; Ibnkahla, M.; Kesidis, G. Balancing Delay and Cost in
593 Virtual Network Function Placement and Chaining. 2018 IEEE 4th International Conference on Network
594 Softwarization and Workshops (NetSoft), 2018, pp. 1–9. doi:10.1109/NETSOFT.2018.8459956.
- 595 14. Leivadeas, A.; Kesidis, G.; Ibnkahla, M.; Lambadaris, I. VNF Placement Optimization at the Edge and
596 Cloud. *MDPI Journal on Future Internet*, 2019, Vol. 11. doi:10.3390/fi11030069.
- 597 15. F., N.; Chawla, N. Using Structural Similarity to Predict Future Workload Behavior in the Cloud.
598 2019 IEEE 12th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD), 2019, pp. 132–136.
599 doi:10.1109/CLOUD.2019.00032.
- 600 16. Ra, M.; Lee, H. Fighting with Unknowns: Estimating the Performance of Scalable Distributed Storage
601 Systems with Minimal Measurement Data. 2019 35th Symposium on Mass Storage Systems and
602 Technologies (MSST), 2019, pp. 1–6. doi:10.1109/MSST.2019.00-21.
- 603 17. Yao, S.; Zhao, Y.; Hu, S.; Abdelzaher, T. QualityDeepSense: Quality-Aware Deep Learning Framework for
604 Internet of Things Applications with Sensor-Temporal Attention. *Proceedings of the 2nd International
605 Workshop on Embedded and Mobile Deep Learning*, 2018.
- 606 18. Prakah-Asante, K.O. and Tonshal, B.; Yang, H.; Strumolo, G.; Chen, Y.; Rankin, J.S. Workload estimation for
607 mobile device feature integration., 2018. US Patent 9,889,862.
- 608 19. Sanchez-Alvarez, D.; Linaje, M.; Rodriguez-Pérez, F. A Framework to Design the Computational Load
609 Distribution of Wireless Sensor Networks in Power Consumption Constrained Environments. *MDPI
610 Sensors* **2018**, *18*.
- 611 20. Pinto Neto, J.B.; Gomes, L.; Ortiz, F.; Almeida, T.; Campista, M.; Kosmalski, M.; Costa, L.; Mitton, N.
612 An Accurate Cooperative Positioning System for Vehicular Safety Applications. *Computers and Electrical
613 Engineering* **2019**.
- 614 21. Laftchiev, E.; Lagoa, C.M.; Brennan, S. Vehicle localization using in-vehicle pitch data and dynamical
615 models. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **2015**, *16*.
- 616 22. Belhajem, I.; Ben Maissa, Y. and Tamtaoui, A. A robust low cost approach for real time car positioning in
617 a smart city using Extended Kalman Filter and evolutionary machine learning. 4th IEEE International
618 Colloquium on Information Science and Technology (CiSt), 2016.
- 619 23. Toldov, V.; Clavier, L.; Loscrí, V.; Mitton, N. A Thompson Sampling Approach to Channel
620 Exploration-Exploitation Problem in Multihop Cognitive Radio Networks. 27th annual IEEE International
621 Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC); , 2016.
- 622 24. Razafimandimby, C.; Loscrí, V.; Maria Vegni, A.; Aourir, D.; Neri, A. A Bayesian approach for an efficient
623 data reduction in IoT. InterIoT 2017 - 3rd EAI International Conference on Interoperability in IoT; , 2017;
624 pp. 1–7.
- 625 25. Li, X.; Mitton, N.; Simplot-Ryl, I.; Simplot-Ryl, D. Dynamic Beacon Mobility Scheduling for
626 Sensor Localization. *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems* **2012**, *23*, 1439–1452.
627 doi:10.1109/TPDS.2011.267.
- 628 26. Ardagna, D.; Panicucci, B.; Trubian, M.; Zhang, L. Energy-aware autonomic resource allocation in multitier
629 virtualized environments. *IEEE Transactions on Services Computing* **2010**, *5*, 2–19.
- 630 27. Chen, C. *Linear system theory and design*; Oxford University Press, Inc., 1998.
- 631 28. Ullah, A.; Li, J.; Shen, Y.; Hussain, A. A control theoretical view of cloud elasticity: taxonomy, survey and
632 challenges. *Cluster Computing* **2018**, *21*, 1735–1764.
- 633 29. Dechouniotis, D.; Leontiou, N.; Athanasopoulos, N.; Christakidis, A.; Denazis, S. A control-theoretic
634 approach towards joint admission control and resource allocation of cloud computing services. *International
635 Journal of Network Management* **2015**, *25*, 159–180.
- 636 30. Leontiou, N.; Dechouniotis, D.; Denazis, S.; Papavassiliou, S. A hierarchical control framework of load
637 balancing and resource allocation of cloud computing services. *Computers & Electrical Engineering* **2018**,
638 *67*, 235–251.

- 639 31. Zhang, W.; Han, B.; Hui, P. On the networking challenges of mobile augmented reality. Proceedings of the
640 Workshop on Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality Network, 2017, pp. 24–29.
- 641 32. Kalatzis, N.; Avgeris, M.; Dechouniotis, D.; Papadakis-Vlachopapadopoulos, K. and Roussaki, I.;
642 Papavassiliou, S. Edge computing in IoT ecosystems for UAV-enabled early fire detection. 2018 IEEE
643 International Conference on Smart Computing (SMARTCOMP). IEEE, 2018, pp. 106–114.
- 644 33. Sonmez, C.; Ozgovde, A.; Ersoy, C. Fuzzy workload orchestration for edge computing. *IEEE Transactions*
645 *on Network and Service Management* **2019**, *16*, 769–782. doi:10.1109/TNSM.2019.2901346.
- 646 34. Guan, G.; Dong, W.; Zhang, J.; Gao, Y.; Gu, T.; Bu, J. Queec: QoE-aware Edge Computing for Complex IoT
647 Event Processing Under Dynamic Workloads. Proceedings of the ACM Turing Celebration Conference -
648 China, 2019.
- 649 35. Jalali, F.; Hinton, K.; Ayre, R.; Alpcan, T.; Tucker, R.S. Fog computing may help to save energy in cloud
650 computing. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* **2016**, *34*, 1728–1739.
- 651 36. Lyu, X.; Tian, H.; Jiang, L.; Vinel, A.; Maharjan, S.; Gjessing, S.; Zhang, Y. Selective offloading in mobile edge
652 computing for the green internet of things. *IEEE Network* **2018**, *32*, 54–60. doi:10.1109/MNET.2018.1700101.
- 653 37. Gao, B.; Zhou, Z.; Liu, F.; Xu, F. Winning at the starting line: Joint network selection and service placement
654 for mobile edge computing. IEEE INFOCOM 2019-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications. IEEE,
655 2019, pp. 1459–1467. doi:10.1109/INFOCOM.2019.8737543.
- 656 38. Leivadreas, A.; Kesidis, G.; Falkner, M.; Lambadaris, I. A graph partitioning game theoretical approach for
657 the VNF service chaining problem. *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management* **2017**, *14*, 890–903.
658 doi:10.1109/TNSM.2017.2732699.
- 659 39. Hegyi, A.; Flinck, H.; Ketyko, I.; Kuure, P.; Nemes, C.; Pinter, L. Application Orchestration in Mobile Edge
660 Cloud Placing of IoT Applications to the Edge. IEEE Int. Wrkshp on Foundations and Applications of Self*
661 Systems, 2016.
- 662 40. Nam, Y.; Song, S.; Chung, J.M. Clustered NFV Service Chaining Optimization in Mobile Edge Clouds.
663 *IEEE Communication Letters* **2017**, *21*, 350–353.
- 664 41. Barcelo, M.; Correa, A.; Tulino, A.; Vicario, J.L.; Morell, A. IoT-Cloud Service Optimization in Next
665 Generation Smart Environments. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communication* **2016**.
- 666 42. Zanzi, L.; Giust, F.; Sciancalepore, V. M2EC: A Multi-tenant Resource Orchestration in Multi-Access Edge
667 Computing Systems. IEEE Int. Conf. on Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC),
668 2018.
- 669 43. Wang, J.; Qi, H.; Li, K.; Zhou, X. PRSFC-IoT: A Performance and Resource Aware Orchestration System of
670 Service Function Chaining for Internet of Things. *IEEE Journal on Internet of Things* **2018**, *5*, 1400–1410.
- 671 44. Cao, J.; Zhang, Y.; An, W.; Chen, X.; Sun, J.; Han, Y. VNF-FG Design and VNF Placement for 5G Mobile
672 Networks. *Springer Journal on Information Sciences* **2017**.
- 673 45. Jemaa, F.; Pujolle, G.; Pariente, M. QoS-aware VNF placement Optimization in Edge-Central Carrier Cloud
674 Architecture. IEEE Int. Conf. on Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), 2016.
- 675 46. Avgeris, M.; Dechouniotis, D.; Athanasopoulos, N.; Papavassiliou, S. Adaptive resource allocation for
676 computation offloading: A control-theoretic approach. *ACM Transactions on Internet Technology (TOIT)*
677 **2019**, *19*, 1–20.
- 678 47. Gupta, R.; Chow, M. Networked control system: Overview and research trends. *IEEE transactions on*
679 *industrial electronics* **2010**, *57*, 2527–2535.
- 680 48. Zhang, W.; Branicky, M.; Phillips, S. Stability of networked control systems. *IEEE Control Systems* **2001**,
681 *21*, 84–99.
- 682 49. Wen, S.; Guo, G. A survey of recent results in networked control systems. *Proceedings of IEEE* **2007**,
683 *95*, 138–162.
- 684 50. Elia, N.; Mitter, S. Stabilization of linear systems with limited information. *IEEE transactions on Automatic*
685 *Control* **2001**, *46*, 1384–1400.
- 686 51. Simon, D.; Robert, D.; Sename, O. Robust control/scheduling co-design: application to robot control. Real
687 Time and Embedded Technology and Applications Symposium (RTAS), 2005.
- 688 52. Xia, F.; Sun, Y. Control-Scheduling Codesign: A Perspective on Integrating Control and Computing.
689 *Dynamics of Continuous, Discrete and Impulsive Systems Series B* **2005**, *13*, 1352–1358.
- 690 53. Branicky, M.; Phillips, S.; Zhang, W. Scheduling and feedback co-design for networked control systems.
691 41st IEEE Conference on Decision and control, 2002.

- 692 54. Bertsekas, D.; Tsitsiklis, J. *Parallel and distributed computation: numerical methods*; Vol. 23, Prentice hall
693 Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1989.
- 694 55. Kashyap, A.; Başar, T.; Srikant, R. Quantized consensus. *Automatica* **2007**, *43*, 1192–1203.
- 695 56. Schenato, L.; Sinopoli, B.; Franceschetti, M.; Poolla, K.; Sastry, S. Foundations of control and estimation
696 over lossy networks. *Proceedings of IEEE* **2007**, *95*, 163–187.
- 697 57. Jungers, R.; Kundu, A.; Heemels, W. Observability and controllability analysis of linear systems subject to
698 data losses. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* **2018**, *63*, 3361–3376.
- 699 58. Athanasopoulos, N.; Jungers, R. Combinatorial methods for invariance and safety of hybrid systems.
700 *Automatica* **2018**, *98*, 130–140.
- 701 59. Dilip, A.; Athanasopoulos, N.; Jungers, R. The impact of packet dropouts on the reachability energy.
702 International Conference on Cyber-Physical Systems (ICCPs), 2018.
- 703 60. Zhang, L.; Hristu-Varsakelis, D. Communication and control co-design for networked control systems.
704 *Automatica* **2006**, pp. 953–958.
- 705 61. Guo, G. A switching system approach to sensor and actuator assignment for stabilisation via limited
706 multi-packet transmitting channels. *International Journal of Control* **2011**, *84*, 78–93.
- 707 62. Wen, S.; Guo, G. Control and resource allocation of cyber-physical systems. *IET Control Theory &*
708 *Applications* **2016**, *10*, 2038–2048.
- 709 63. Martí, P.; Camacho, A.; Velasco, M.; Gaid, M. Runtime allocation of optional control jobs to a set of
710 CAN-based networked control systems. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* **2010**, *6*, 503–520.
- 711 64. Tabuada, P. Event-triggered real-time scheduling of stabilizing control tasks. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic*
712 *Control* **2007**, *52*, 1680–1685.
- 713 65. Abdelrahim, M.; Postoyan, R.; Daafouz, J.; Nei, D.; Heemels, M. Co-design of output feedback laws and
714 event-triggering conditions for the L2-stabilization of linear systems. *Automatica* **2018**, *87*, 337–344.
- 715 66. Donkers, M.; Heemels, W. Co-design of output feedback laws and event-triggering conditions for the
716 L2-stabilization of linear systems. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* **2012**, *57*, 1362–1376.
- 717 67. Goebel, R.; Sanfelice, R.; Teel, A. Hybrid dynamical systems. *IEEE Control Systems Magazine* **2009**, *29*, 28–93.
- 718 68. Matveev, A.; Savkin, A. *Estimation and control over communication networks*; Springer Science & Business
719 Media, 2009.
- 720 69. Garoche, P. *Formal verification of control system software*; Princeton University Press, 2019.

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